

DEVELOPMENT OF READY TO EAT FRUIT FLAKES

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Abstract— Ready to eat foods are processed to be ready to eat with very little additional efforts. The main objective of this project is to develop a cereal mix that can be used as breakfast. Ready to eat Indian Fruit Flakes was developed by using dried papaya, apple and banana flakes. Its sensory evaluation (consumer acceptance test) revealed that the product was liked moderately by the consumer. The various parameters such as moisture, colour, non enzymatic browning, total sugars and reducing sugars were analysed. The Iron and Calcium content was found to be in high ratio during the analysis. The microbial load was found to be within the safe limit. Total Plate Count, Yeast and Mould were found to be within limits. Salmonella were found to be absent. The ready to eat fruit flakes can be prepared by adding it to boiled milk with addition of sugar if needed. The development of RTE food without losing the traditional taste are found to be more acceptable by the present day society.

Index Terms— Banana, Condiments, Dried Apple, Papaya.

I. INTRODUCTION

Food choices are driven by three needs: convenience, taste, health and nutrition. Convenience foods are the foods that can be prepared with less effort by the customers. Consumers are looking forward to convenient foods that can be easily prepared and served. Convenience food is a concept that is prevalent in the world since long, while its conception into the Indian market has been seen recently. This type of food is becoming popular because it saves time and labour.

The Ready to Eat food has extended shelf life and is available in the market very easily. The convenience of the product can be basically classified into two categories: shelf stable convenience food and frozen convenience foods [1]. Shelf table foods are further classified as ready to eat (RTE), ready to cook (RTC) and ready to serve (RTS).

Ready to eat (RTE) foods are known as the processed formulations suitable for human consumption without further cooking. RTC foods are those foods which are not completely cooked, but the ingredients are semi cooked. The RTC product should be either boiled in water or oil for few minutes before consumption. Ready to Cook foods must be brought to a temperature sufficiently to kill any pathogenic microorganisms before it is safe to consume.

During the project an innovative healthy ready to eat Indian fruit flakes was prepared by drying papaya, banana and apple along with the addition of dried grapes and cashew. After the development of fruit flakes, it can be further reconstituted by addition of milk and sugar if needed.

Drying is a process used to remove the moisture content from the food product. Drying is an excellent method for preserving a wide variety of heat sensitive materials such as protein, microbe etc. The shelf life of food can be extended by drying. Air drying and hot air oven drying are different drying methods used for drying. Air Drying is an ancient process used to preserve food. Hot air oven drying was the method used to dry the fruits [3].

Papaya is a common man's fruit with high nutritive value.

It also contains natural vitamins and minerals rich in Vitamin A and Vitamin C. It is also an excellent source of antioxidants [4]. Bananas have good nutritional content of vitamins and minerals as well as they are rich in carbohydrates [6].

Fruit flake is a ready to eat breakfast cereal. The effort was to develop a ready to eat fruit flakes which provides enrichment of Calcium and Iron [9]. Using dried ingredients one can make ready to eat breakfast cereal that matches the current consumer trend. The success relies on the methods and selection of right choice of ingredients.

RTE fruit flake is a new developed product. Different food industries have developed other types of flakes. The production of RTE fruit flakes involves the use of dried ingredients that help in the enrichment of Iron and Calcium. The general aim of this product development was to increase the iron and calcium levels in the consumer. In today day and age, people tend to consume less fruits especially children. By incorporating essential fruits into the diet, we aim to develop the nutritional profile of the consumer. This is a product that appeals to people of all age group.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Raw Materials

The following materials were procured from the local market for processing and product development: Apple, banana, papaya, cashew and raisins were used as ingredients.

2.2 Pre preparation of ingredients

Finely sliced pieces of apple (2kg), papaya (2.5kg) and banana (2kg) were cleaned and dried in hot air oven.

Figure 1: Sliced ingredients

2.3 Method

2kg of apple, 2.5kg papaya and 2kg of banana was first procured from a local market. The raw materials must be free from blemishes, insect or fungal infection. They must have appropriate maturity. Slicing of apple, papaya and banana was done. It was then kept in a hot air oven for drying and to remove moisture. Drying was done at 70 0 C for all the materials. Banana was dried for 7-10 hours. Papaya was dried for 9-11 hours and apple also was dried for 9-11 hours. Drying is done to remove as much as moisture as possible to prevent microbial growth .After that the sliced materials are roasted. Roasting is a cooking method that uses dry heat , where hot air envelops the food cooking it evenly on all sides with temperature of atleast 110 0 C for 2-3 minutes [12]. Roasting enhances the flavour through caramelization and Mailard browning on the surface of the food. After roasting the sample is kept for cooling at room temperature. Papaya is roasted for 3.5 minutes. Banana is roasted for 2 minutes and apple is roasted for 2.5 minutes.Raisins and cashewnuts are added for extra flavour.The mixture can then be mixed with milk and it can be served.

Table 1: Formulation of composition of fruit flakes per 100g

Ingredient	Quantity
Banana	40g
Papaya	45g
Raisins	2g
Cashew	3g
Apple	10g

Various samples and batches were used to get the appropriate texture of flakes. Some of the planned ingredients such as

kiwi and grapes could not be used due to off odours and flavours developed during the drying process [14]. Standard hot air dryer was used for the process. The apparatus required for the processes such as knives, cutting boards etc. were sterilized. All the processing mechanism took place in hygienic conditions. Various shapes and size of the fruits were used in order to obtain the desired flavour and texture. Overheating or roasting of the samples were prevented after initial batches of few samples were cooked badly. After the sample preparation sensory analysis of the products were done by a team of sensory analysts. Their scorecard is given in the sensory analysis section. The product prepared can be consumed with milk, buttermilk etc. Heating of the product is desired to get extra crispiness and texture. The product was found to be free for microbial contamination and was safely stored. The product can be consumed during any part of the day without any excessive preparation.

Figure 2: Fruit flakes

2.4 Calculation of Yield and Cost

It is important to estimate the yield and cost percentage to calculate how profitable our product can be when released in the market. The methods used are applied in the food processing industry [15].

2.4.1 Yield Percentage

It can be calculated by the weight percentage of the raw material before and after drying.

$$\text{Yield percentage} = \frac{\text{weight of sample after drying}}{\text{weight of sample before drying}} \times 100$$

2.4.2 Cost

The cost of each ingredient was calculated for a mixture of 100g. The cost of 1g sample of each ingredient was calculated after taking into consideration the yield and wastage and profitability was analysed.

3. Analysis of Chemical Characteristic

III. MOISTURE ESTIMATION

Weigh accurately about 5 gram of the sample in a previously dried dish. Place the dish inside the moisture analyser. The analyser uses IV radiation to analyse the moisture content. The moisture analyser works according to the thermo-gravimetric princip

3.2 Determination of Total Ash Content

Ash is the residue obtained after food stuff is ignited until it is free from carbon usually at a temperature of 6000C.

A crucible is weighed to constant weight.

About 2grams of the material is placed in the crucible and its weight determined.

The crucible containing the material is placed in a muffle furnace at 6000C until a white ash is obtained (for 2.5 hours).

The ash content is weighed for constant weight after successive cooling and heating operations.

Calculations:

$$\text{Total ash (\%)} = \frac{(W3-W1) @}{(W2-W1)} \times 100$$

Where W1 is the weight of the crucible in (g) , W2 is the weight of the crucible + sample(g) , W3 is the weight of the crucible + ash (g)

$$\text{Weight of the sample (g)} = (W2-W1)$$

$$\text{Weight of the ash (g)} = (W3-W1)$$

3.3 Determination of Acid insoluble ash

Boil the ash for 5 minutes with 25ml HCl and filter it through a filter paper.

Then it is washed with hot distilled water.

The contents are then transferred to a crucible (filter paper).

The crucible is kept in a muffle furnace and dried at 6000C for 2.5 hours until the ash is obtained.

The ash obtained is then cooled in a desiccator and weighed.

Acid insoluble ash % = (Weight of acid insoluble ash/weight of spice sample) x 100

IV. MICROBIOLOGICAL ASSAY

4.1 Total Plate Count

The samples were prepared by mixing 50g of sample in 450ml of phosphate buffer. Serial dilutions up to 10⁻⁶ were prepared and 1ml of each dilution was pipette on to sterile petri plates and then plate count agar was poured and solidified. These plates were incubated at 350C for 2 days. The colonies were counted in Quebec's colony counter (BAM 2013)

$$N/\{(1 \times n1) + (0.1 \times n2) \times d = \sum C$$

Where,

N= Number of colonies per ml or g of product

$\sum C$ = Sum of all colonies on all plates

n1 = Number of plates in first dilution counted

n2= Number of plates in second dilution counted

d=Dilution from which the first counts were obtained

4.2 Salmonella

25gram of sample was added to 225ml buffered peptone water. Incubate at 35 0 C for 16-18 hours. For secondary enrichment from the above made mixture 0.1ml to 10ml Rappaport – Vassiliadis and 1ml to 10ml Tetrathionte broth was transferred and were incubated. Then selective streaking of incubated TT broth and RV medium were done on Bismuth sulphite agar , Xylose lysine desoxycholate agar ,

and Hektoen enteric agar. These plates were incubated at 350C for 24 hours.

4.3 Yeast and mould

25gram sample was added to 225ml of 0.1% peptone water. Serial dilutions up to 10⁻⁴ were prepared then each dilution were pipette on to three plate of pre poured solidified DRBC agar plates and was spread using L rods. These plates are then incubated at 250C for 5 days

$$N = \sum C / \{(1 \times n1) + (0.1 \times n2) \times d$$

Where,

N= Number of colonies per ml or g of product

$\sum C$ = Sum of all colonies on all plates

n1 = Number of plates in first dilution counted

n2= Number of plates in second dilution counted

d=Dilution from which the first counts were obtained

All microbial tests were conducted according FSSAI methods [18].

V. SENSORY EVALUATION

Sensory evaluation involves the use of human senses for the purpose of evaluating a product. It is an analytical method in which human senses serve as a measurement tool to determine the quality and/or to describe the condition of food product. Pre requisites for the success of the analytical process include : standardization of method , regular training and performance measurement of testers , a statistical evaluation of test results and standardisation of terms. The sensory tests were conducted based on 9 point hedonic scale for the evaluation of fruit flakes [20].

Table 2 for evaluation of score

card

Score/Rating	Standard hedonic scale
9	Like extremely
8	Like very much
7	Like moderately
6	Like slightly
5	Neither like or dislike
4	Dislike slightly
3	Dislike moderately
2	Dislike very much
1	Dislike extremely

The criteria for sensory analysis was based on

- Appearance
- Colour
- Odour
- Flavour
- Taste
- Overall acceptability

Sensory evaluation is often described as a scientific method used to evoke, measure, analyse and interpret those responses to products as perceived through the senses of sight, smell, touch, taste and hearing

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Ready to eat fruit flakes was prepared by utilization of dried apple, dried papaya and dried banana as the major ingredients. The acceptability of product is checked by sensory evaluation. The nutrient, chemical and microbial analysis of the fruit flakes were carried out.

6.1 Nutrient analysis

The nutrient analysis of the fruit flakes was carried out by a separate lab facility. The product has a high amount of carbohydrates of about 73.74%. It has a protein content of 4.40%. The fat content was 1.98%. It gives us energy of 330.38Kcal per 150g. The ash content is 2.46% and moisture is 17.42%. Calcium is 24% and Iron is 23%. Note that all values are taken into consideration with respect to sample quantity as 150g. Calcium and Iron was tested as banana, apple and papaya are good sources of such nutrients.

Table 3 Nutritional profile of fruit flakes

Test	Result
Moisture	17.42%
Total ash	2.46%
Protein	4.40%
Fat	1.98%
Sugar	32.02%
Carbohydrate	73.74%
Energy	330.38cal
Calcium	24%
Iron	23%
Acid Insoluble ash	0.092%

6.2 Sensory evaluation

The sensory quality of the sample was evaluated by an expert panel of judges on a 9- point hedonic scale. The fruit flakes were served at room temperature to the panel of judges. The sensory parameters analysed were appearance, flavour, aroma, texture and overall acceptability. Average of the scores given by the panel members for each sensory parameter was taken. Sensory evaluation of the sample was carried out inside the sensory booth. Fruit flakes were mixed with milk before sensory evaluation was done.

Table 4 : Average score of panellists

Parameter	Score
Appearance	7
Flavour	8
Aroma	8
Texture	7
Overall Acceptability	8

Appearance	7
Flavour	8
Aroma	8
Texture	7
Overall Acceptability	8

The above table gives us an average score about the sensory evaluation of the sample. It was found out that apple and papaya gave more taste and flavour compared to banana. The texture was acceptable due to roasting of the fruits. However in certain samples uneven thickness of the banana flakes was an issue. This can be solved by proper slicing. Mixing the flakes with milk seemed to enhance the flavour and taste of the flakes. Mixing of milk lead to an increase in the softness of flakes hence making it easier to consume and tasty. The addition of kismis and nuts to the flakes enhanced flavour and aroma while also increasing its nutritional profile. It had a pleasant aroma and flavour. Perfect drying and roasting times could perhaps improve the flavour and texture of the flakes. It cannot be left outside in the open as contamination may occur due to the moisture content in the flakes. This can be prevented by longer drying periods. Environmental changes may cause food deterioration. It can affect the taste and can have an impact on the nutritive value. Effective packaging can prevent spoilage. Overall the product was found to be liked moderately with scope for improvement.

6.3 Microbial analysis

The sample is subjected to microbial analysis and tests are done for TPC, Yeast and mould and salmonella. The sample was found to be safe from salmonella. TPC and yeast and mould were found to be within the range required.

The TPC obtained is mentioned in the table. The number of colonies was less than 40; it indicates the good quality of the final product. The TPC of the fruit flakes were found to be within safe limits. The yeast and mould count was found to be absent which indicate that no spoilage occurred. Salmonella was also found to be absent in the sample. The acid content present in fruits was found to inhibit the growth of microbes in the sample leading to an increase in the shelf life of the fruit flakes. Proper drying can remove excess moisture and prevent contamination.

Table 5 : Microbial Analysis of fruit flakes

	0 th day	10 th day	15 th day
TPC	Nil	Nil	<30cfu/g
Salmonella	Nil	Nil	Nil
Yeast and mould	Nil	Nil	Nil

Figure 3: Microbial Test

6.4 Chemical analysis

6.4.1 Moisture

Moisture was analysed using IR method.

Moisture % = 8.57

6.4.2 Total ash

Weight of ash = 0.0543g

Weight of sample = 2.001g

Ash% = (weight of ash/ weight of sample) x 100
= 2.713%

6.4.3 Acid insoluble ash

Weight of acid insoluble ash = 0.002g

Weight of spice sample = 2.001g

Acid insoluble ash% = (Weight of acid insoluble ash/weight
of spice sample) x 100
= 0.099%

6.5 Yield and cost analysis

Initial quantity of raw material: Banana – 2kg
Papaya – 2.5kg
Apple – 2kg
Raisins and cashew – 15g

Quantity of material after peeling: Banana – 1.65kg
Papaya – 2.2kg
Apple – 1.8kg
(Raisins and cashew were

added as it is)

Quantity of material after drying: Banana – 157.5g
Papaya – 144g
Apple – 85g

Yield percentage of each fruit: Banana (%) = $(157.5 / 1650) \times 100 = 9.54\%$

Papaya (%) = $(144 / 2200) \times 100 = 6.54\%$

Apple (%) = $(85 / 1800) \times 100 = 4.72\%$

Therefore the yield percentages of banana, papaya and apple are given above respectively. The cost analysis is then done keeping in mind the yield so that the product can be priced to generate profit.

CONCLUSION

Ready to Eat Fruit flakes was developed by using fruits such as apple, papaya and banana along with cashew and raisins. It is a new product with a unique recipe of its own. It can be eaten by all age groups. It can taste better with the addition of milk. No added sugars or preservatives are used. Nutritional analysis of the product was done. The product had

a high amount of carbohydrates of about 73.74%. It has a protein content of 4.40%. The fat content was 1.98%. It gives us energy of 330.38Kcal per 150g. The ash content is 2.46% and moisture is 17.42%. Calcium is 24% and Iron is 23%. Overall acceptability was found to be 8 after sensory evaluation by the judges. The product was found to be microbiologically stable. There was no presence of Salmonella and TPC and yeast and mould were found to be within limits. Chemical properties and physical properties like ash, moisture etc. was found out. Only moisture needed correction. The fruit flakes can be consumed with milk and eaten within few minutes.

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